

GENE FLOW FROM IMIDAZOLINONE HERBICIDE-RESISTANT RICE CULTIVARS TO WEEDY RICE (ORYZA SATIVA L.)

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ABSTRACT

Imidazolinone (IMI) herbicide-resistant rice technology has been used more two decades to the control of weedy rice in worldwide rice fields. In herbicide-resistant crop management technology such as the IMI resistant rice, outcrossing or cross hybridization is a possible issue. The objective of this study was to determine the mechanism of IMI herbicide resistance in weedy rice as well as the prevalence of known IMI-resistant genes. Weedy rice samples which are 116 suspected IMI resistant plants were collected in 2020 in Turkey. The survival plants' seed samples were gathered at harvest time after the application of Imazamox from Bafra and Terme Valley IMI-resistant rice production fields. Seeds were planted under greenhouse conditions and a double dose of imazamox (106 g ai ha⁻¹) was applied to 21-day-old seedlings in a spray chamber. Double dose imazamox application experiment revealed that 39 plants survived. DNA samples were extracted from the surviving samples and Sanger DNA sequencing was performed for the acetolactate synthase (ALS) gene region. Single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) was detected in 29 samples which is S563T, but no substitution was detected in 10 samples. This SNP point is the mutation point that constitutes the source of resistance of resistant materials such as Luna CL, Rekor Cl, Iskender CL, Kopru CL, Ozgur CL widely grown in the region. It has been estimated that the cause of resistance of the IMI resistant weedy rice samples might be 25% of the gene flow from IMI resistant rice varieties, and 8.6% of other resistance mechanism such as off-target resistance and other mutations. It has been concluded that IMI rice technology efficacy has significantly decreased to control weedy rice. In addition to cultural measures such as crop rotation in the control of weedy rice, new resistance sources are needed in monoculture rice cultivation system.

Keywords: Weedy rice, imazamox, herbicide resistant crops, gene flow.

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